

RESEARCH REPORT

July, 2023

TREPA Series 08-2023

Lab Assessment Protocol

PREPARED BY:

Barbara Wolfe and Meredith L. Gore

TREPA

**Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals**

TREPA PUBLICATION SERIES

This publication is one of a series of scholarly products resulting from investigations of human dimensions of global environmental change. The Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals studies risk at the intersection of human-wildlife conflicts and diseases of animals using a team science approach.

A LIST OF TREPA PUBLICATIONS MAY BE OBTAINED BY ACCESSING OUR WEBSITE AT:

www.conservationcriminology.com/trepa/

CITE THIS DOCUMENT:

Wolfe, B., and Gore, M.L. **Lab Assessment Protocol**. Threat Reduction for the Environment, People and Animals. Department of Geographical Sciences, College of Behavioral and Social Sciences, University of Maryland, College Park. College Park, MD. 7 pp.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to express our appreciation to the administrators and laboratory personnel of the University of Pretoria Department of Veterinary Tropical Diseases, the Office of Veterinary Research, and the State Laboratory of Skukuza in South Africa, and the Biotechnology Centre of the University of Eduardo Mondlane and the Central Veterinary Laboratory of Mozambique, who participated in this study. For their assistance during all phases of the research, we express our thanks to Drs. Henriette van Heerden, Fabiola Quesada, Gianluca Zaffarano, and Alonso Aguirre.

Thank you to Dr. Mary Louise Penrith for assistance with preparation of the protocol.

This project was sponsored by the Department of Defense, Defense Threat Reduction Agency. The content of the information does not necessarily reflect the position or the policy of the federal government, and no official endorsement should be inferred.

INTRODUCTION

The protocol depicted in this document was utilized to conduct an assessment of the capacity of laboratories in South Africa and Mozambique for diagnosis of zoonotic and other diseases present in the respective countries. Controlled and notifiable diseases, such as *Bacillus anthracis*, were highlighted. The report resulting from this assessment is: TREPA Series 17-2023: Wolfe, B.A et al. **2023 Animal Disease Diagnostic Laboratory Capacity Assessment**. Threat Reduction for the Environment, People and Animals. Department of Geographical Sciences, College of Behavioral and Social Sciences, University of Maryland, College Park. College Park, MD. 60 pp. GL

PROTOCOL

For each laboratory, record or assess the following, preferably by an in-person visit with photographic support. Alternatively, if an in-person is not possible, details may be obtained by a written questionnaire.

I. Organizational Details	
a. Name:	
b. Location:	
c. Main contact details:	
d. Type of laboratory (government, private or non-governmental organization):	
e. Purpose of laboratory (commercial, primarily diagnostic or research):	
f. Registration status (nationally and internationally):	
g. Is it subject to regular inspections?	
h. Funding source and annual budget:	
i. Name of head of laboratory and qualifications:	
j. Staff complement and qualifications:	
k. If possible, level of experience and years in service:	
l. Evidence of training record:	
II. Laboratory Facilities	
a. Description of laboratory facilities:	
b. Biosecurity level and systems in place:	
c. General cleanliness and organization of laboratory:	

d. Structural stability of the laboratory building:	
e. Electrical and hot and cold-water supply, as well as 24/7 backup power supply availability:	
f. Equipment available and current state of equipment:	
g. Equipment calibration and maintenance schedule/records:	
h. Appropriate waste disposal system:	
i. Safety documentation available:	
j. Sample storage capacity:	
k. Sourcing and storage of supplies:	
III. Sample Receiving and Shipping	
a. Catchment of samples:	
b. Annual sample throughput:	
c. Sample identification system:	
d. Accessibility to road, rail, and air transportation services:	
e. Ability to outsource samples to labs outside of GLTFCA (nationally and internationally):	
IV. Diagnostic Capacity	
a. Bacteriology/Microbiology i. Bacterial culture and identification (to what level)	
b. Chemistry/Toxicology	
c. Clinical Pathology i. Blood chemistry ii. Hematology iii. Cytology	
d. Molecular Diagnostics (PCR)	

i. Quantitative or conventional	
e. Parasitology i. Fecal egg counts ii. Parasite identification (which groups)	
f. Serology i. Range of techniques/tests	
g. Pathology i. Gross pathology – field and/or laboratory ii. Histopathology	
i. Virology i. Virus isolation/tissue culture ii. Serum neutralization	
V. Quality Management and Accreditation	
a. Quality management system in place:	
b. Test accreditation	
c. Which tests are performed? By what authority are they accredited?	
d. Policy for non-conforming testing and test results	
VI. Information System and Reporting	
a. Record keeping and reporting systems in place	
VII. Future Planning	
a. Planned development within the next 12 months:	
b. Long-term strategy or 5-year plan:	